

THE IMPORTANCE OF OFFENSES PREVENTION AMONG STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation: This article presents thoughts and reflections on the concepts of student, pupil, cadet, listener, offense prevention, offense prevention among university students, offense among university students, legal measures, organizational measures, social measures, and mechanisms for implementing spiritual and educational measures.

Keywords: Student, pupil, cadet, trainee, offense, measures for the prevention of offenses among students, factors contributing to the commission of offenses by students.

In the world, issues of improving legal education, ensuring its effective and targeted implementation, increasing legal literacy, increasing the effectiveness of the fight against offenses through the use of new forms and mechanisms of legal propaganda, and introducing modern information and communication technologies into the activities of crime prevention are becoming increasingly relevant not through strengthening repressive measures to prevent and combat offenses, but through early prevention of offenses.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, five years ago As noted in his Address to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 24, 2020: "If we all unite, constantly study, perform our work perfectly and productively, acquire modern knowledge, and strive forward without sparing ourselves, our life and society will certainly change."

It is no coincidence that in the aforementioned address, the head of our state emphasized the importance of education, learning, acquiring modern knowledge, and consolidation. Because without education, without increasing literacy, in particular, without increasing legal literacy, it is impossible to achieve the goal set in the field of crime prevention.

Therefore, the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022-2026 also provides for the creation of an effective system for the timely identification and elimination of the conditions for the commission of offenses, the organization of legal and educational activities to form a legal culture among the population in conjunction with the teaching of the rich history, scientific and cultural heritage, national and religious values of our people.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Strategy "Uzbekistan-2030" serves as a solid legal basis for enhancing the potential of youth and their comprehensive development.

It should be noted that in our country there is a tradition of assigning a special name to each year and, based on it, adopting documents related to the state program. In order to enhance human dignity, ensure the interests of the population, and build a strong economy in our country 2024 has been declared the "Year of Supporting Youth and Business." In recent years, every young person feels in their lifestyle and activities the attention paid to young people, the care shown to them, and the conditions and opportunities created for them.

The rights and interests of the younger generation are also specifically enshrined in the Constitution in the new edition.

In particular, a separate chapter on Family, Children, and Youth has been allocated in the new version of the Constitution.

Article 79 of the Basic Law stipulates that the state ensures the protection of the personal, political, economic, social, cultural, and environmental rights of youth, encourages their active participation in the life of society and the state, and creates conditions for the intellectual, creative, physical, and moral formation and development of youth, the realization of their rights to education, healthcare, housing, employment, and leisure.

Raising a harmoniously developed generation and constantly caring for the growing youth is one of the most important and priority areas of the policy being implemented under the leadership of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev. It is gratifying that today a new generation is being formed in Uzbekistan, which perceives the world in a new way, considers its fate united with the fate of its people and Homeland.

They equally assimilate the spiritual heritage of their ancestors, universal values, and intellectual discoveries. Knowledgeable, wise, and enterprising youth, whose hearts are filled with a sense of national pride and love for the Motherland, are the main force that determines the potential and future of any country. Young people study in various educational institutions, selflessly work in all spheres of public life, and make a worthy contribution to the reforms and creative work being carried out in the country.

Students studying in higher educational institutions have a serious impact on the development of society and, at the same time, determine the prospects for development, indicating the level of scientific and intellectual potential of each country. Because for the growth of the country's economy and culture, the introduction of scientific achievements into the national economy, students of higher educational institutions must possess deep theoretical knowledge and practical skills.

Therefore, in developed countries, the number of students per capita is high. After Uzbekistan gained independence, the number of students in the country increased significantly. In our country, every graduate of a general education school, academic lyceum, and vocational college has the right to become a student.

A student can study at the expense of the state, as well as on a contract basis. In our country, students receive higher education in two stages: bachelor's and master's degrees.

The student is considered the most socially active, active, and dedicated part of every country. For their direct engagement in mastering science, students are considered the intellectually advanced stratum of society. Therefore, great attention is paid to the deep professional and spiritual-moral training of students.

In order to prevent offenses among students and work with them individually, 155 prevention inspectors and 3020 tutors have been established in 112 state higher educational institutions.

In 2024, based on a joint decision of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation, the Ministry of Defense, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the Ministry of Youth Policy and Sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "Qalqon" public groups were established in each higher education institution to educate university students in the spirit of military patriotism, promote the protection of

public order, prevent offenses and combat crime, and contribute to the stabilization of the socio-spiritual environment in higher education institutions.

In Uzbekistan, a number of measures are being taken to ensure the active participation of students in the life of the country, to create opportunities for them to fully master the idea of national independence. In addition, for the social protection of students in Uzbekistan, all of them are provided with scholarships, students in need of housing are provided with accommodation, and opportunities are created for young people to participate in various scientific, artistic, and sports clubs. Holding universiades among students once every 2 years contributes to a certain extent to their growth as physically healthy and spiritually mature individuals.

However, analysis shows that, despite the positive work being carried out, the share of crimes committed by students of higher educational institutions is significantly increasing.

In the first quarter of 2025, 460 crimes were committed by student youth in the capital.

In the first quarter of 2025, 460 crimes were committed by young people in the capital. This is 39.8% higher than in the same period last year (in the first quarter of 2024, this figure was 329). Among students, this indicator increased by 7.8 percent.

The names of higher educational institutions in the capital, whose students commit the most crimes, were also revealed.

By state universities:

1st place: Tashkent State Transport University - 27 people.

2nd place: Tashkent State Technical University - 21 people.

3rd place: National University of Uzbekistan - 20 people.

4th place: Tashkent State University of Economics - 19 people.

5th place: Tashkent State University of Law - 12 people.

By non-state universities:

1st place: ISFT - 23 people.

2nd place: Alfraganus University - 20 people.

3rd place: International University of Chemistry - 19 people.

When analyzing crimes by type:

Road traffic accident - 72

Theft - 57 units

Drug addiction - 46

Bodily injuries - 41

Hooliganism - 24

Robbery - 11

Murder - 5

Robbery - 5

Rape - 2

Others - 48.

Therefore, it is important for the university administration, faculty, and officials, in cooperation with internal affairs bodies, to pay special attention to the prevention of offenses among students. Today, as a result of insufficient development of legal literacy, legal culture, and legal awareness among students, the illegal circulation of psychotropic and potent narcotic drugs (lyric, tramadol), as well as synthetic narcotic drugs (stimulators and

hallucinogens), which are popular among them as light narcotics, have a serious impact on the criminogenic situation.

Law enforcement agencies are taking a number of measures to prevent the spread of such drugs and narcotic drugs among students of higher educational institutions.

Recently, online gambling has become an integral part of the lives of some students of higher educational institutions. As a result of such games, there are many cases of falling not only under the financial influence, but also under the emotional influence that leads to addiction.

One of the unfortunate cases is the illegal organization of gambling games that are alien to our national traditions and mentality, as well as our religious views, especially spreading online and drawing students of higher educational institutions into their trap. There are even cases where people lose large sums of money in such games and ultimately commit suicide or commit crimes to pay for lost money.

The illegal organization and conduct of gambling and risk-based games in our country is defined as a crime under Article 278 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Moreover, illegal participation in such games, as well as gambling and other games based on risk, is recognized as an administrative offense under Article 191 of the Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Administrative Responsibility.

In particular, the illegal organization or conduct of gambling and other games based on risk, including the creation or maintenance of gambling establishments for such games, is punishable by imprisonment for up to seven years.

No one has won in online gambling and risk-based games, and it's impossible. The reason is that the creators of this program effectively used the capabilities of artificial intelligence and strong psychologists.

Unfortunately, it is unfortunate that the number of students who have lost and fallen into debt in gambling is increasing, and they are resorting to crime in order to earn money. Another issue is that in today's era of globalization, when ideological conflicts are escalating, threats aimed at poisoning the minds of young people on the Internet and social networks are becoming increasingly apparent.

Unfortunately, as a result, among students of some higher educational institutions, there are cases of adherence to mass culture, immorality, crime, drug addiction, alcoholism, disrespect for national and religious values, extremism, and radicalism.

Preventive measures carried out among students of higher educational institutions are a consistent, complex, long-term process that ensures the gradual creation of appropriate legal views in the student environment.

It is based on a system of quantitative calculations of the use of available forces and resources for the implementation of preventive measures for the prevention of offenses among students of higher educational institutions.

Implementation of crime prevention among students of higher educational institutions, combating crime is a personal, specific, and objective task of the university. Its solution is carried out within the framework of fulfilling the more general, strategic tasks of the educational institution.

The activities of the subjects of crime prevention in higher educational institutions should be based on certain basic principles, a specific model. For the resolution of offenses

among students, it is necessary to develop a specific concept. Because there is no legal framework regulating the procedure for resolving disputes between students.

It is necessary to identify and eliminate the causes and conditions of offenses committed among students of higher educational institutions, as well as to eliminate the causes and conditions that contribute to the commission of offenses by forecasting future offenses. In this regard, not only law enforcement officers, but also the leadership and responsible employees of higher educational institutions should strengthen their work in this direction.

Preventive work among students should be carried out comprehensively, systematically, based on a single plan and concept, from a single management center. The organizer and manager of this work is the head of the higher educational institution, and the direct organization and coordination of all preventive measures should be carried out by the crime prevention service.

Early prevention of offenses in higher educational institutions is a process that requires a comprehensive, systematic approach. In this process, improving the methodological foundations of prevention, using innovative approaches, and cooperation between all stakeholders will increase effectiveness. Crime prevention is crucial for maintaining peace and order in society and ensuring the safety of citizens.

This process should be carried out not only with the participation of law enforcement agencies, but also with the participation of families, educational institutions, the public, and the media. By forming a sense of legal culture and respect for the law in every citizen, it is possible to prevent crime and offenses. If preventive measures are effectively organized, stability and prosperity will be ensured in society.

One of the main directions of prevention is the strengthening of legal advocacy among the population, the effective teaching of law in schools and higher educational institutions, and the meaningful organization of young people's free time. Individual work with individuals prone to committing offenses is also of great importance. In this regard, preventive conversations, control, and targeted work methods conducted by internal affairs bodies will yield effective results. Every citizen should be well acquainted with the laws, know their rights and obligations, and respect the rule of law in society. Because the most important factor in preventing offenses is a person's own consciousness and upbringing. Therefore, the effectiveness of prevention depends not only on state bodies, but also on each person.

Currently, many forms of offenses are observed in society. Such situations often arise among young people due to a lack of legal knowledge and culture, unemployment, shortcomings in education and upbringing, and the influence of the family environment.

Therefore, the prevention of offenses should be carried out in cooperation with all members of society - state bodies, educational institutions, families, mahallas, and the media.

Offense - a culpable unlawful act (action or inaction) for which administrative or criminal liability is provided;

Crime prevention - a system of legal, social, organizational, and other measures of general, special, individual, and victimological crime prevention applied to maintain and strengthen law and order, identify and suppress offenses, as well as identify and eliminate the causes and conditions contributing to their commission.

Offences among students of higher educational institutions - a culpable unlawful act (action or inaction) committed among students of higher educational institutions, entailing administrative or criminal liability;

Prophylaxis of offenses among students of higher educational institutions - this is a system of legal, social, organizational, and other measures of general, special, individual, and victimological prevention of offenses, applied for the purpose of maintaining and strengthening law and order, identifying and suppressing offenses, as well as identifying and eliminating the causes and conditions contributing to their commission.

Regarding the concept of "prevention of offenses among students of higher educational institutions," based on the above analysis, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1) prophylaxis of offenses among students of higher educational institutions - the activity of subjects of crime prevention, providing for the implementation of preventive measures;

2) these measures are aimed at:

a) formation in students of respect for the law and an intolerant attitude towards any manifestation of violation of the law and early prevention of offenses among them;

b) identification, study, elimination (disinfection) of the causes of offenses among students and the conditions contributing to them;

c) education of students prone to committing offenses;

g) reducing the risk of students becoming victims of offenses.

It is advisable to divide the measures serving the prevention of offenses among students of higher educational institutions into the following priority areas:

Legal measures - measures aimed at forming and improving the legal framework for working with students. Currently, the activities of state administration bodies, local government bodies, and civil society institutions in this area are not sufficiently regulated by law. Analysis of current legislation shows that none of the bodies carrying out the prevention of offenses have clear grounds for working with students. In our opinion, in improving the legal framework for working with students, along with defining the specific tasks of the relevant subjects in this area, it is also necessary to develop the organizational and legal framework for cooperation between them. As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized, from now on, internal affairs bodies, the prosecutor's office, the Youth Union, the Women's Committee, the mahalla, and other state and non-state organizations must take timely measures to prevent unemployment, drug addiction, neglect, family conflicts, and other such negative phenomena that contribute to crime and offenses. It is also necessary to avoid commonality, strive for a common goal, work together, and approach each problem based on a clear plan^[1].

Social measures. In some literature, when discussing the prevention of offenses, special emphasis is placed on social prevention. Indeed, in the commission of offenses and social factors play a significant role in the formation of the offender's personality. In particular, social factors mainly contribute to the formation of the student body and the commission of offenses by them. The fact is that an individual's unemployment, exclusion from studies and military service occurs as a result of social reasons. For example, the unemployment of a person with the appropriate education and profession, or the denial of military service to a person fit for military service, leads to their alienation from society.

In our opinion, the following social measures should be implemented in the prevention of offenses among students: studying the objective and subjective reasons that prevent students from finding their place;

studying existing opportunities for social support of students, further increasing them in the future;

development of measures to ensure the employment of students by involving them in entrepreneurship;

Taking appropriate measures for students to spend their free time productively, etc.

Organizational measures. The effectiveness of working with students of higher educational institutions depends on the level of viability and optimal organization of measures in this area.

In this matter, special attention should be paid to:

appropriate measures should be aimed at broad cooperation of relevant subjects, corresponding to the real-life situation, the physical capabilities of the subjects involved in working with students, as well as other daily tasks;

being a coordinator of the internal affairs bodies;

wide involvement of students themselves in the implementation of the established measures;

speed of information exchange;

evaluation of results, etc.

Spiritual and moral measures. Spiritual and moral issues are also of particular importance in the prevention of offenses among students of higher educational institutions.

Failures of students (failure to get a job, complicated examination processes, etc.) also negatively affect their spiritual and moral values. This can lead to dissatisfaction with the current system and the formation of legal nihilistic views. Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to conducting large-scale educational activities among students.

Measures of educational influence among students of higher educational institutions should cover all stages of the education system, as well as extracurricular processes. Special attention should be paid to the popularization of physical culture and sports among them. Because sports, by strengthening the health of the population, educating the younger generation as healthy and harmoniously developed individuals, establishes a healthy lifestyle in society, and prevents various diseases and harmful habits. Sport also plays an important role in the formation of high culture and patriotic feelings. Achievements in this area make the country known to the world and inspire pride in all compatriots.[\[1\]](#).

Based on the foregoing, it should be noted that the prevention of offenses among students is a national and public affair. Effectiveness in this area can be achieved only through the systematic organization and consistent conduct of work on identifying and suppressing offenses among students of higher educational institutions, as well as identifying the causes and conditions contributing to their commission.

Thus, based on the presented considerations, the following conclusion can be drawn: prevention of offenses among students of higher educational institutions - the activities of the subjects of crime prevention aimed at forming in students respect for the law and an intolerant attitude towards any manifestations of law violations, early prevention of offenses among students, identification, study, elimination of the causes of their commission and the conditions contributing to them, upbringing of students prone to committing offenses, implementation of preventive measures aimed at reducing the risk of students becoming victims of offenses.

1. Factors causing offenses among students of higher educational institutions can be grouped as follows:

- Socio-economic factors (unemployment, lack of material support);

- Spiritual and moral weakness (low level of legal consciousness);
- Influence of the family environment;
- Ineffective organization of free time.

2. Existing problems in the early prevention of offenses:

- Lack of systematic organization of preventive work;
- Ineffectiveness of legal education measures in universities;
- Insufficient organization of individual work with students;
- Lack of social partnership (e.g., internal affairs, mahalla, parents).

3. Proposals for improving methodological approaches:

A) Conducting promotional work using modern methods:

Media content (videos, appearances on social networks);

Demonstrate legal situations using practical examples through simulation and training.

B) Formation of students as individuals with a legal culture:

Conducting regular events, such as the Month of Legal Knowledge;

Implementation of psychological and legal counseling centers.

C) Implementation of interactive learning methods: debates, forums, case studies (problem analysis), role-playing games.

G) Strengthening cooperation between educational institutions and mahallas, law enforcement agencies:

Establishment of the activities of preventive councils;

Implementation of a mentoring system (strengthening control with the help of older students)

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